

Downey and Tucker "Providing long hay in a novel pipe feeder or a bucket reduces some, but not all abnormal oral behaviors in milk-fed dairy calves"

Supplemental Table 1. Model outputs for feed (grain, hay, TMR) intake and water intake in the preweaning and weaning periods, and average daily gain (ADG) during the preweaning period.

Preweaning model results												
Anova (type III SS)											R2	
Variable	DF*	Treatment chisq	p-value	DF*	Week chisq	p-value	DF*	Interaction chisq	p-value	Marginal	Conditional	
Grain intake	2	0.0837	0.959	1	610.9628	<0.0001	2	16.3002	0.0003	0.605	0.922	
Hay intake	1	0.1307	0.718	1	564.8023	<0.0001	1	12.4669	0.0004	0.856	0.917	
Water intake	2	0.0745	0.963	1	182.1746	<0.0001	2	10.8247	0.004	0.142	0.549	
ADG (kg/d)	2	2.313	0.315	1	32.7354	<0.0001	2	7.8241	0.02	0.307	0.307	

Weaning model results												
Anova (type III SS)											R2	
Variable	DF*	Treatment chisq	p-value	DF*	Day chisq	p-value	DF*	Interaction chisq	p-value	Marginal	Conditional	
Grain intake	2	4.2943	0.117	1	5.5896	0.018	1	1.7468	0.4175	0.156	0.846	
TMR intake	2	2.6423	0.267	1	26.131	<0.0001	1	2.7882	0.2481	0.115	0.628	
Water intake	2	6.9268	0.032	1	0.0317	0.859	1	7.1041	0.029	0.088	0.724	

Overall ADG + final BW

Variable	Control		Bucket		Pipe		One-way ANOVA	
	Raw average (SE)	95% CI	Raw average (SE)	95% CI	Raw average (SE)	95% CI	F-value	p-value
Overall ADG (kg/d)	0.541 (0.03)	[0.473,0.610]	0.681 (0.03)	[0.13,0.748]	0.633 (0.04)	[0.534,0.732]	4.2	0.027
Final BW (kg)	69.1 (1.8)	[64.9,73.3]	77.9 (6.0)	[71.8,83.9]	75.0 (3.5)	[67.0,83.0]	2.716	0.086

*Numerator DF obtained from the Anova type III SS are presented; denominator DF are known to be erroneous in many mixed models and are not presented (e.g. <https://stat.ethz.ch/pipermail/r-help/2006-May/094765.html>)

In reviewing the model summary to confirm conservative analysis outside of DF output, "Calf" is correctly identified as the group (27 calves), and estimates are produced for all 7 weeks when the identity variance model is used.

Supplemental Table 2. Back-transformed model-predicted means, SE, and 95% CI for all oral behaviors scored, along with model outputs.

Back-transformed model predicted means (proportions; obtained using *type="response"* in emmeans in R) and CI:

Behavior	Week 4						Week 6					
	Control		Bucket		Pipe		Control		Bucket		Pipe	
	Emmeans (SE)	95% CI										
Ruminating	0.149 (0.012)	[0.126,0.175]	0.254 (0.017)	[0.223,0.289]	0.241 (0.016)	[0.210,0.275]	0.143 (0.012)	[0.12,0.168]	0.237 (0.016)	[0.207,0.271]	0.258 (0.017)	[0.226,0.293]
NNOM: Pipe	0.005 (0.0007)	[0.003,0.006]	0.004 (0.0006)	[0.003,0.005]	0.002 (0.0005)	[0.001,0.003]	0.004 (0.0007)	[0.003,0.006]	0.002 (0.0004)	[0.001,0.003]	0.002 (0.0004)	[0.001,0.003]
NNOM: Other	0.085 (0.009)	[0.068,0.106]	0.051 (0.006)	[0.040,0.066]	0.052 (0.007)	[0.040,0.067]	0.093 (0.010)	[0.075,0.115]	0.056 (0.007)	[0.044,0.072]	0.049 (0.006)	[0.038,0.064]
NNOM: Total	0.090 (0.010)	[0.072,0.111]	0.055 (0.007)	[0.043,0.070]	0.054 (0.007)	[0.042,0.069]	0.097 (0.010)	[0.078,0.119]	0.058 (0.007)	[0.046,0.074]	0.052 (0.006)	[0.040,0.066]
Grooming	0.030 (0.004)	[0.023,0.039]	0.031 (0.004)	[0.024,0.041]	0.033 (0.004)	[0.025,0.043]	0.031 (0.004)	[0.024,0.040]	0.032 (0.004)	[0.025,0.042]	0.036 (0.005)	[0.028,0.047]
Tongue flicks	0.033 (0.002)	[0.028,0.038]	0.027 (0.002)	[0.023,0.031]	0.027 (0.002)	[0.023,0.032]	0.030 (0.002)	[0.025,0.035]	0.029 (0.002)	[0.024,0.033]	0.027 (0.002)	[0.023,0.031]
Eating (overall)	0.016 (0.002)	[0.012,0.021]	0.060 (0.006)	[0.049,0.072]	0.049 (0.005)	[0.040,0.059]	0.017 (0.002)	[0.013,0.023]	0.068 (0.006)	[0.056,0.081]	0.058 (0.005)	[0.048, 0.070]
Eating (grain)	0.016 (0.002)	[0.012,0.021]	0.016 (0.002)	[0.012,0.021]	0.021 (0.003)	[0.016,0.027]	0.017 (0.002)	[0.013,0.022]	0.019 (0.002)	[0.014,0.024]	0.023 (0.003)	[0.018,0.030]
Eating (hay)	-	-	0.042 (0.007)	[0.030,0.058]	0.027 (0.005)	[0.018,0.038]	-	-	0.047 (0.007)	[0.034,0.065]	0.033 (0.006)	[0.023,0.047]
Drinking water	0.005 (0.0007)	[0.003,0.006]	0.006 (0.0009)	[0.005,0.008]	0.005 (0.0007)	[0.004,0.006]	0.004 (0.0006)	[0.003,0.005]	0.007 (0.001)	[0.006,0.010]	0.006 (0.0008)	[0.004,0.008]
Sucking milk	0.007 (0.0004)	[0.007,0.008]	0.008 (0.0004)	[0.007,0.008]	0.007 (0.0004)	[0.007,0.008]	0.006 (0.0003)	[0.006,0.007]	0.008 (0.0004)	[0.008,0.009]	0.007 (0.0003)	[0.006,0.008]

Model results:

Pairwise comparisons and p-values are only presented if the overall effect is significant

Behavior	Anova (type III SS)						R2 estimates					
	Treatment			Week			Interaction			Marginal		Conditional
	DF*	chisq	p-value	DF*	chisq	p-value	DF*	chisq	p-value			
Ruminating	2	45.1277	<0.0001	1	1.1792	0.2775	2	2.5305	0.2822	0.655	0.889	
Control v. Bucket	-	-	0.0001	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Control v. Pipe	-	-	<0.0001	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Bucket v. Pipe	-	-	0.981	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
NNOM: Pipe	2	11.0269	0.004	1	7.0397	0.008	2	3.5853	0.1665	0.277	0.536	
Control v. Bucket	-	-	0.0783	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Control v. Pipe	-	-	0.007	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Bucket v. Pipe	-	-	0.5888	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Week 4 v. Week 6	-	-	-	-	-	0.0446	-	-	-	-	-	
NNOM: Other	2	18.227	0.0001	1	0.6057	0.4364	2	0.9877	0.6103	0.367	0.753	
Control v. Bucket	-	-	0.0032	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Control v. Pipe	-	-	0.0011	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Bucket v. Pipe	-	-	0.9339	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
NNOM: Total	2	19.7347	<0.0001	1	0.2618	0.6089	2	0.7025	0.7038	0.382	0.749	
Control v. Bucket	-	-	0.0024	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Control v. Pipe	-	-	0.0007	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Bucket v. Pipe	-	-	0.9013	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Grooming	2	0.615	0.7353	1	0.0546	0.8152	2	0.1213	0.9412	0.023	0.603	
Tongue flicks	2	3.391	0.1835	1	0.3942	0.5301	2	1.5258	0.4663	0.099	0.373	
Eating (overall)	2	104.2256	<0.0001	1	2.2125	0.1369	2	0.3202	0.8521	0.796	0.894	
Control v. Bucket	-	-	<0.0001	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Control v. Pipe	-	-	<0.0001	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Bucket v. Pipe	-	-	0.282	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Eating (grain)	2	4.2019	0.1223	1	1.4823	0.2234	2	0.2125	0.8992	0.129	0.619	
Eating (hay)	1	3.3236	0.0683	1	2.7217	0.099	1	0.2685	0.6044	0.164	0.703	
Drinking water	2	6.9614	0.0308	1	1.4809	0.2236	2	4.519	0.1044	0.205	0.634	
Control v. Bucket	-	-	0.0308	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Control v. Pipe	-	-	0.4771	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Bucket v. Pipe	-	-	0.3172	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Sucking milk	2	6.6082	0.0367	1	2.5617	0.1095	2	10.7887	0.0045	0.238	0.573	
Week 4:	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Control v. Bucket	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.9311	-	-	
Control v. Pipe	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.9286	-	-	
Bucket v. Pipe	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.7489	-	-	
Week 6:	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Control v. Bucket	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0011	-	-	
Control v. Pipe	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.291	-	-	
Bucket v. Pipe	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0.0639	-	-	

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In reviewing the model summary to confirm conservative analysis outside of DF output, "Calf" is correctly identified as the group (27 calves)

Downey and Tucker “Providing long hay in a novel pipe feeder or a bucket reduces some, but not all abnormal oral behaviors in milk-fed dairy calves”

Supplemental Figure S1. Bucket and pipe set up for Control (left), Bucket (middle), and Pipe (right) treatments. Control calves had grain, water, and empty buckets (left to right) and an empty pipe feeder; Bucket calves had grain, water, and hay buckets (left to right) and an empty pipe feeder; Pipe calves had grain, water, and empty buckets (left to right) and a hay pipe feeder. Perforated rubber mats placed on top of sand bedding for newborn calves (d 0-5) are seen in the middle and right photos. All treatments had access to buckets and pipes beginning on d 0. At the start of step-down weaning (50-60 d), TMR was provided for Control and Pipe calves in the empty bucket (right) and for Hay calves in place of hay (right).

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Supplemental Figure S2. Starter grain fed to all treatments (left; Starter Calf Feed 901033, Associated Feed and Supply Co.), and long chop (~19 cm) of mountaingrass hay fed to Bucket and Pipe treatment calves (right)

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Materials needed:

- 10.2 cm wide PVC pipe
- 10.2 cm DWV Insert Test Cap with Knockout cap (e.g. Oatey Co.)
- 10.2 cm B-vent pipe hanger (e.g. Speedi-Products BV-PH)
- 6.35 cm drill bit hole saw attachment
- Drill
- Saw

Methods:

1. Cut PVC pipe into 56 cm sections with a saw
2. Mark the following points on the pipe starting from one end: 8.2 cm, 21.4 cm, 34.6 cm, 47.8 cm
3. Line the drill bit at the center of the 6.35 hole saw attachment up with the marked locations and drill the holes (4 total); the center of each hole will be at the marked locations

4. Sand down the holes and pipe ends: Start with a very coarse sandpaper, then move to a medium grain, and finish with a very fine grain
5. If pre-cut PVC pipe or a hand saw was used, the end caps will already fit; if a high-powered saw was used, the heat may have caused the pipe ends to slightly expand so the end caps will be loose. Put 4 small drops of glue (e.g. Original Gorilla Glue, The Gorilla Glue Company) around the side of the end cap and allow to dry. Once dry, the end caps will fit snugly but still be easy to remove

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Photo 1: Empty pipe after sanding

Photo 2: Empty pipe attached to pen

Photo 3: Pipe with hay attached to pen

Supplemental Figure S3. Instructions for creating PVC pipe feeders.

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Supplemental Figure S4. Overall percentage of 24-h observations spent drinking water in wk 4 and 6 compared to amount of water consumed on the corresponding day. Each point represents an individual calf.

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Supplemental Figure S5. Overall percentage of 24-h observations engaged in tongue rolling in wk 4 and 6. Each colored line represents an individual calf.

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Supplemental Figure S6. Percentage of time engaged in tongue rolling in wk 4 and 6 by individual calf averaged over 15-min bins in a 24-h day. Each colored line represents a different calf. Dashed lines represent milk feedings, which occurred at 09:30 and 16:30 h.